

Kinetic and Mechanistic Study of the Substitution Reaction of the Aquo-ligands from Hydroxopentaaquochromium(III) Ion by 2-Pyridylacetic Acid

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The title reaction has been studied spectrophotometrically. The following rate law has been established in the pH range 4.64–5.3,

$$\frac{d[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})(\text{PyAcO})_2]}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}]_{\text{Total}} [\text{PyAcOH}]}{1 + K_E [\text{PyAcOH}]}$$

where, K_E is ion-pair equilibrium constant between the two reacting species and k_a the rate constant for conversion of outersphere complex into innersphere complex. The reaction rate is found to be pH-dependent in the pH range 4.46–5.3. The reaction rate is higher compared to the rate of isotopic water exchange process of the same substrate complex. Activation parameters have been calculated. A mechanism involving outersphere associative equilibrium between the two reacting species followed by associative interchange (I_a) for outersphere complex to product has been suggested.

AQUO-ligand substitution reactions on Cr^{III} centre have been studied extensively¹⁻⁷ and different mechanisms have been proposed. Study with hydroxopentaaquochromium(III) ion has not been received similar attention. Hydroxide ion plays an important role by virtue of its σ as well as π bonding ability. Naturally, some interesting results are expected in the study of anation reactions of hydroxo-aquochromium complex. Anation reactions of the titled substrate complex were carried out by Thusius⁸ with simple anions like Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- etc. The non-dependence of rate on $[\text{Ligand}]$ for such reactions led the author to propose a dissociative mechanism with an argument that OH^- in $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ labilises the *trans*- H_2O -ligand facilitating a dissociative process. But for the anation of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ by sulphate and fluoride, a lower $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and a negative $\Delta S^\ddagger$ claimed an associative mechanism. Thus different mechanism may be operative for the anation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ depending on the nature of the incoming ligand.

We planned to study the anation reaction of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ by a series of bidentate and tridentate ligands with the hope that such studies will enrich the mechanistic idea in this area. The present communication deals with the results obtained in the anation of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ by 2-pyridylacetic acid—a bidentate (N–O donor) ligand.

Experimental

Hexaaquochromium(III) perchlorate was prepared⁹ using A.R. grade chemicals. Hydroxopenta-

aquochromium(III) (Complex-I) was prepared *in situ* from hexaaquo complex by adjusting the pH to 5.0. The difference between the hexaaquo- and the hydroxopentaaquo-chromium(III) perchlorate can be established from their spectral behaviour. $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ shows absorption maxima at 410 nm ($\log \epsilon = 1.15$) and 575 nm ($\log \epsilon = 1.01$), but Complex-I shows absorption maxima at 430 nm ($\log \epsilon = 1.447$) and 590 nm ($\log \epsilon = 1.255$). The product of the reaction between $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and 2-pyridylacetic acid was prepared by mixing them in different molar ratios, viz. 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 40 thermostated at 50° for 48 h. All the spectra except that of 1 : 1 exhibited the same nature having λ_{max} at 400 and 540 nm. Considerable shifting of λ_{max} values of the product with high ϵ compared to those of Complex-I indicated a good complexation by the ligand. The composition of the product in solution was determined by Job's method of continuous variation. The metal–ligand ratio was found to be 1 : 2. For isolation of the solid product, a mixture of Complex-I and the ligand (1 : 2 molar ratio) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h, concentrated and finally treated with acetone. Analysis of the isolated maroon coloured solid revealed the composition $[\text{Cr}(2\text{-PyAcO})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ for the product (Complex-II). Spectral observation for the solution of the isolated solid was the same as obtained earlier for the product in solution.

All the kinetic runs were followed spectrophotometrically at 540 nm where the spectra of Complex-I and Complex-II differ widely. A Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer was used for the absorbance measurements. NaClO_4 was used for the maintenance of proper ionic strength during the kinetic

studies. NaOH/HClO₄ was used for the adjustment of pH; a Systronics digital pH meter was used. Equal volume of solutions in ethanol-water of 2-pyridylacetic acid and Complex-I of desired concentration were mixed in a reaction vessel and kept at the desired temperature. The composition of the reaction mixture was such that the first order rate law is applicable and pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were obtained graphically by plotting log [(*D*_∞ - *D*₀)/(*D*_∞ - *D*_{*t*})] against time. *D*₀, *D*_{*t*} and *D*_∞ are the O.D. value initially, after time *t* and after completion of the reaction, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying [Complex-I] on reaction rate: At a fixed excess concentration (0.075 M) of 2-pyridylacetic acid, ionic strength (*μ*) 0.05 M and pH 5.0, the [Complex-I] was varied. The values of *k*_{obs} were found to be 5.7 × 10⁻⁴, 5.5 × 10⁻⁴ and 5.6 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ at [Complex-I] of 0.0025, 0.0035 and 0.004 M, respectively, at 35°. The experimental data indicates that the rate of reaction is first order with respect to [Complex-I],

$$\frac{d[\text{Complex-II}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Complex-I}]$$

Effect of varying pH on rate constant: The rate of reaction increased with the increase of pH of the medium. At a fixed [Complex-I] (0.0025 M), [2-PyAcOH] (0.037 M), *μ* (0.05 M) and temperature 35°, the pseudo-first-order rate constants *k*_{obs} (× 10⁴) were 1.74, 2.42, 3.43, 4.17 and 5.80 s⁻¹ at pH 4.64, 4.80, 5.0, 5.16 and 5.3, respectively. Thus the rate of reaction increased with the increase in pH of the medium and the effect is considerable at the higher range of pH studied. This effect of pH variation on rate can be explained from the p*K* values of the aquo complex¹⁰ and the entering ligand¹¹. The ligand has two dissociative groups and from the following equilibria it can be assumed that upto pH 5.0 the ligand remains mainly in zwitterionic form,

but between pH 5.0 to 5.3 the percentage of the anionic form of the ligand increases. The donor ability is higher for the anionic species compared to that of zwitterionic one which is noticed in the higher *k*_{obs} values at pH 5.16 and 5.3. Change in rate with the variation of pH is due to the variation of the nature of Complex-I also. Considering the acid dissociation equilibrium,

it is clear that at pH 3.8 the percentage of the hexaquo species and the hydroxopentaaquo species is approximately same at the experimental temperature. But the increase in pH increases the percentage of the more reactive hydroxopentaaquo species. Enhanced reactivity of the hydroxopentaaquo species is due to well known labilising effect of the hydroxide ion adjacent to the water molecule by virtue of its lone-pair of electron capable of exerting strong electromeric effect.

Effect of varying [2-PyAcOH] on rate constant: At a fixed [Complex-I] (0.0025 M), ionic strength (0.05 M) and pH 5.0, the concentration of the ligand was varied in the range of 0.025–0.075 M. The values of *k*_{obs} obtained are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANTS (*k*_{obs}) WITH [2-PyAcOH] AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

pH=5.0 and *μ*=0.05 M

[2-PyAcOH] M	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹) at				
	25°	30°	35°	36°	38°
0.0250	0.9	1.1	2.2	2.5	3.5
0.0375	1.3	1.7	3.1	3.5	4.7
0.0500	1.7	2.1	4.1	4.3	6.0
0.0625	2.0	2.5	5.0	5.1	6.7
0.0750	2.4	2.8	5.4	5.7	7.6

It can be noted that the rate of reaction increases with the increase in [Ligand] but approaches a limiting value at high [Ligand]. The fact is due to ion-pair formation which is completed at the high ligand concentration. The following reaction scheme can be proposed to explain the nature of variation of incoming ligand concentration on reaction rate,

The rate equation for the anation can be deduced in the form,

$$\frac{d[\text{Cr}(\text{PyAcO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}]_{\text{Total}} [\text{PyAcOH}]}{1 + K_E [\text{PyAcOH}]}$$

$$= k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}]_{\text{Total}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or, } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{PyAcOH}]}{1 + K_E [\text{PyAcOH}]} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } 1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_a + 1/k_a K_E [\text{PyAcOH}] \quad (3)$$

where K_E is ion-pair equilibrium constant and k_a is rate constant for interchange of outersphere complex to innersphere complex. So the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[PyAcOH]$ should be a straight line with an intercept of $1/k_a$ and a slope of $1/k_a K_E$. This is found to be the same for all the temperatures studied (Fig. 1). The k_a values determined from the intercepts are $9.5, 14.0, 17.1, 20.0$ and $25.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $25, 30, 33, 35$ and 38° , respectively, whereas K_E values remain almost constant ($4-6.2$) in the temperature range $25-38^\circ$.

Effect of varying ionic strength on rate constant :
 The [Complex-I], ligand concentration, pH and temperature were kept constant at 0.0025 M , 0.0375 M , 5.0 and 35° , respectively. It was observed that the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were 3.10×10^{-4} , 3.34×10^{-4} and $3.22 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for ionic strength $0.1, 0.2$ and 0.3 M , respectively. Thus variation of μ by NaClO_4 did not alter the rate of reaction which is expected for a reaction involving a cationic and a zwitterionic species. But when the ionic strength of the medium was altered by NaNO_3 , the rate of reaction was found to increase. The k_{obs} values for $\mu=0.1$ and 0.2 M (adjusted by NaNO_3) were 6.83×10^{-4} and $7.71 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. It may be due to the fact that the non-substituting nitrate ion facilitates the metal-water bond fission through its specific attack on the coordinated water molecule. Consequently, labilisation of water molecules catalyses the entry of the ligand and hence the increase in rate is observed. This typical type of ionic strength effect was observed by different authors^{1,2-14}.

Fig. 1. Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[PyAcOH]$ at different temperatures : (A) 25° , (B) 30° , (C) 33° , (D) 35° and (E) 38° .

Scheme 1

Effect of temperature on reaction rate: The reaction rate was followed at five different temperatures for different [Ligand] to find out the effect of temperature on the values of rate constants for interchange process. Activation parameters were calculated from the linear Eyring plot of $\log k_a$ vs $1/T$ and the values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are 54.8 kJ mol^{-1} and $-118.9 \text{ J K mol}^{-1}$, respectively.

Mechanism and conclusion: The anation rate constants (k_a) for the present system were much higher than the isotopic water exchange rate of the same substrate⁹ complex. This indicates the associative character of the interchange process, i.e. bond formation by the incoming ligand plays a significant role in the interchange process. The bond formation by the incoming ligand in the transition state gives up some amount of energy which compensates partly the energy required for the metal-water bond fission. This compensation is reflected in the lower value of enthalpy of activation. The activated complex formation through outer-sphere association is significantly stabilised by hydrogen bonding. The large negative $\Delta S^\ddagger$ value indicates such compact activated state formation as

represented in Scheme 1. All the above facts suggest that the reaction proceeds through an associative interchange (I_a) process.

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